

Deliverable D5.4 Report on KPI

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE: Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services (871075)		
Project Acronym (EC Call):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE (H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020)		
WP No & Title:	WP5 Demonstrator Projects		
WP leader(s):	Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	23 - UiB		
Contractual delivery date:	30/05/2023	Actual delivery date:	26/06/2023
Delayed:	1 month		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	UIB, HITS, BSC, INRAE, CNRS, UNILU		
<p>Authors: Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon (INRAE), Laura Portell-Silva (BSC), Salvador Capella-Gutierrez (BSC), Marina Popleteeva (UNILU)</p> <p>Contributors: Inge Jonassen (UiB); Federico Bianchini (UiO), Espen Åberg (UiB/UiT), Adam Hospital (IRB Barcelona), Nils P Willassen (UiB/UiT), Ferran Sanz (UPF), Ernesto Picardi (CNR), Pinar Alper (UNILU), Vilém Ded (UNILU), Nene Djenaba Barry (UNILU), Teresa d'Altri (CRG), Marko Vidak (UL), Corinne Martin (ELIXIR-hub)</p> <p>Acknowledgments (not grant participants):</p>			
Reviewers:	ELIXIR-CONVERGE Management Board (MB) members.		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
09/06/2022	0v1	Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon (INRAE)	Initial version
16/06/2023	0v2	Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon (INRAE)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
19/06/2023	0v3	Juan Arenas (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission

26/06/2023	0v4	Anne-Françoise Adam-Blondon (INRAE)	MB comments addressed
05/07/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	1
2. Contribution toward project objectives	2
3. Introduction	4
4. Description of work accomplished	5
4.1 Development of a first set of KPIs, allowing to monitor progress in the development of ELIXIR-CONVERGE resources in the context of the use cases	5
4.2 Assessment of the adoption by community of users	6
5. Results	7
4.1 Monitoring the progress in the development of CONVERGE's resources in the context of the use cases	7
4.2 Engagement of communities and success stories	9
4.2.1 - Assessment of dissemination efforts in the context of the use cases	9
4.2.2 - Success stories showing interest and adoption by communities of users	9
Use case 1. Harmonised FAIR plant genotype & phenotype data management toolkit for Europe	9
6. Conclusions	10
7. Impact	11
8. Next Steps	12
9. Deviation from Description of Action	13

1. Executive Summary

The overall goal of ELIXIR-CONVERGE's WP5 was, based on the analysis of a set of very diverse use cases, to contribute to the development of a set of resources supporting the development and implementation of Data Management Plans (DMPs) in national and transnational projects. Six use cases were considered to co-develop and test a method to address domain specific data management planning associated to a set of resources in collaboration with WP1, WP2 and WP3. In this context, another objective of WP5 was to **develop, implement and refine key performance indicators (KPIs) in order to monitor the**

demonstrator projects’ implementation of data management plans and possibly assess their adoption by the relevant community.

WP5 developed two sets KPIs in collaboration with WP4, in charge of developing KPIs across the entire ELIXIR-CONVERGE project and for assessing the impact of the project :

- a first set aiming at monitoring the development of guidance, resources for the development of DMP and for training in the context of the use cases
- a second set aiming at addressing the adoption of these resources by relevant communities of users as a way to assess the impact of the work achieved

In parallel, in order to ensure long term maintenance/update of the developed resources and to increase their impact, WP5 started to engage with ELIXIR communities that could be natural owners of these resources.

The KPI developed and collected by WP5 during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project were useful to follow the partner’s progress in the development and test of a sort of starter kit for domain specific data management support. Success stories could be collected showing adoption by communities and new projects and were mapped on ELIXIR’s categories of impacts showing already “hits” on several of these.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	No
Key Result 1. 2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	No
Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models	No

incorporated into national strategies	
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	No
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	No
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	No
Key Result 3.4: Enable ‘FAIR at source’ practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	No
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	Yes
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	Yes

Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	Yes
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	Yes
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	No

3. Introduction

The overall goal of ELIXIR-CONVERGE's WP5 was, based on the analysis of a set of very diverse use cases¹, to contribute to the development of a set of resources supporting the development and implementation of Data Management Plans (DMPs) in national and transnational projects. Six use cases were considered:

1. Harmonised FAIR plant genotype & phenotype data management toolkit for Europe
2. Reproducible, comparable and FAIR Epitranscriptomics
3. Common Data management plans for the marine metagenomics Community
4. Federated access to human genomics data: GDPR
5. FAIR encoding and access to Toxicology data
6. FAIR organisation of biomolecular simulation information

These efforts resulted in the development of a method to address domain specific data management planning associated to a set of resources co-produced by WP1, WP2 and WP3: the RDMkit and its content², the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) and its knowledge model³ as well as the learning path templates and guidance developed by the ELIXIR Training platform. ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP5 co-developed DMP guidance through the development of new RDMkit pages and DSW improvements^{4,5} as well as an analysis of training resources and gaps through the development learning paths in the context of its use cases⁶.

¹ Adam-Blondon A-F, Alper P, Capella-Gutierrez S, Faria D, Portell Silva L, Hospital A, Willassen N-P (2021) ELIXIR-CONVERGE D5.1 Categorisation of the pilot projects. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4674491>

² <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

³ <https://ds-wizard.org/>

⁴ Portell L, Capella-Gutierrez S, Alper P, d'Altri T, Hospital A, Åberg E, Faria D, Adam-Blondon A-F, Collin O, Willassen N-P, Lieby P, Oulas A, Pafilis E, Jareborg N, Fatima N, Åkerström WN, Picardi E (2021) ELIXIR-CONVERGE D5.2 Report on the first two DMP processes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5139903>

⁵ Capella-Gutierrez S, Popleteeva M, Bianchini F, Åberg E, Hooft R, Schuánek M, Slifka J, Hospital A, Willassen NP, Piñero J, Sanz F, Ramirez-Anguila JM, Pastor M, Mayer MA, Picardi E, Alper P, Ded V, Djenaba Barry N, Lieby P, d'Altri T, Faria D, Le Floch E, Rocca-Serra P, Droesbeke B, Bösl K, Vidak M (2023) Deliverable D5.5 Report on the remaining four DMP processes

⁶ Leskošek B, Haurheeram V, Bianchini F, Alper P, Portell-Silva L, Åberg E, Hospital A, Popleteeva M, Willassen NP, Vidak M, Adam-Blondon A-F, Collin O, Curwin A, Freeberg M, Le Floch E, Lieby P, Picardi E, Capella-Gutierrez S (2023)

Another objective of WP5 was to **develop, implement and refine key performance indicators (KPIs) in order to monitor the demonstrator projects' implementation of data management plans and possibly assess their adoption by the relevant community**. These KPIs should contribute to identifying potential gaps when implementing DMPs to be addressed in collaboration with WP1, WP2 and WP3. Finally, KPIs' use and adoption were to be evaluated with WP1 (Best practice, Operating models) and WP4 (Impact assessment) to produce relevant indicators which can be adopted beyond the proposal itself.

WP5 developed its KPIs after a round of discussions with WP5 partners but also with a WP4 partner in charge of developing KPIs across the entire ELIXIR-CONVERGE project and for assessing the impact of the project.

4. Description of work accomplished

ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP5 developed and collected two sets of KPIs:

- a first set aiming at monitoring the development of guidance, resources for the development of DMP and for training in the context of the use cases
- a second set aiming at addressing the adoption of these resources by relevant communities of users as a way to assess the impact of the work achieved

In parallel, in order to ensure long term maintenance/update of the developed resources and to increase their impact, WP5 started to engage with ELIXIR communities that could be natural owners of these resources.

4.1 Development of a first set of KPIs, allowing to monitor progress in the development of ELIXIR-CONVERGE resources in the context of the use cases

The KPIs that allow monitoring the progress in terms of development of resources supporting DMPs in the context of the use cases are quantitative. They are listed in Table 1. They were collected at mid-term and end of the project. Each KPI was associated with a target to be reached that was chosen by consensus with WP5's partners.

Table 1. KPIs allowing to monitor the development of resources in support to Data Management Planning in the context of the Use Cases of ELIXIR-CONVERGE

Category of resource	DMP templates	Digital Resources		People
KPI	KPI-1: Number of use case-driven revision of DSW Knowledge Model @ DSW	KPI-2: Number of RDMkit domain page	KPI-3: Number of RDMkit tools assembly page	KPI-4: Number of analysis of the training gaps
Target	All use-cases (6)	All use-cases (6)	Specific contributions (at least 2)	All use-cases (6)

4.2 Assessment of the adoption by community of users

ELIXIR-CONVERGE’s WP5 aimed at facilitating the development of DMPs for new projects in the domains of application addressed through WP5’s use cases. Testing the usefulness of the resources developed in such new projects necessitates in first place their dissemination in communities of potential users, to stimulate possible use and adoption.

ELIXIR Communities are instruments set up by ELIXIR to ensure a liaison with specialised communities of researchers in order to tailor ELIXIR’s services towards the needs of these communities of users⁷[1]. ELIXIR-CONVERGE’s use cases were mapped to the ELIXIR communities (Table 2): the only use case that could not be “homed” in an ELIXIR community was the use case 2 “FAIR Epitranscriptomics”. The partners involved in other use cases were encouraged to engage with the relevant ELIXIR community as a way to disseminate, test and possibly sustain on the long term the work achieved. This was achieved mainly in the context of the use cases 1 and 4 by presenting the resources developed in community’s meetings or other projects. Engagement was also worked out by engaging members of the ELIXIR communities or of other relevant projects in WP5’s activities, in particular in the context of the use case 1.

Table 2. Mapping of the use cases developed in ELIXIR-CONVERGE with the ELIXIR communities.

Use Case	ELIXIR Community
Harmonised FAIR plant genotype & phenotype data management toolkit for Europe	Plant Science
Reproducible, comparable and FAIR Epitranscriptomics	

⁷ <https://elixir-europe.org/communities>

Common Data Management Plans for the Marine Metagenomics Community	Marine Metagenomics
Federated access to human genomics data: GDPR	Federated Human Data, Rare diseases
FAIR encoding and access to Toxicology data	Toxicology
FAIR organisation of biomolecular simulation information	3D-Bioinfo

Finally, a critical analysis of the work achieved in the context of two use cases was presented to WP1 monthly meetings, which involves as partners some of the data stewards of ELIXIR’s national nodes, as well as to national and international communities of users and to stakeholders in the context of data management in life sciences.

Quantitative indicators of the dissemination efforts targeted to specific communities can be collected, I-5 : number of oral presentations and posters delivered. KPI-5 does not capture the involvement in co-development of the resources. We did not define a target to reach for this indicator.

Quantitative indicators showing use and adoption are more difficult to collect at such a short time after the delivery of the resources. It was therefore proposed to list a first set of success stories in terms of adoption of these resources as a first measure of the impact of the work achieved. In addition, such stories might be re-used to improve communication on the outputs of the project.

5. Results

The results in terms of development of resources supporting data management planning in specific domains of application as well as in terms of adoption by users and by other important stakeholders for their sustainability are described in the sections below. Following progress with the two chosen sets of KPIs allows us to analyse the successes, opportunities and remaining challenges to be met in the development as well as in the adoption phase.

4.1 Monitoring the progress in the development of CONVERGE’s resources in the context of the use cases

The first assessment of the progress in the development of resources supporting data management planning in the context of the 6 use cases was made at mid-term of the project (Table 3). All the use cases but one had developed a domain page in the RDMkit, giving specific guidance on data management and cross linking with supporting tools, data standards, ontologies and training resources (KPI-2). Three use cases were able to develop a

tool assembly (KPI-3) and the Data Stewardship Wizard knowledge model was reviewed for all the use cases (KPI-1) resulting in a new and improved version.

The conclusion of this first phase is that the method set up to develop specific resources in the RDMkit portal in ELIXIR-CONVERGE was efficient provided that a suitable community of experts is available to spend a few days together to gather the knowledge available and to write the pages.

Table 3. Assessment of the project’s progress at mid-term and end.

Category of resource	DMP templates	Digital Resources		People
KPI	KPI-1: Number of use case-driven revision of DSW Knowledge Model @ DSW	KPI-2: Number of RDMkit domain page	KPI-3: Number of RDMkit tools assembly page	KPI4: Number of analysis of the training gaps
Mid-project	3	5	3	0
End of the project	6	6	4	6

Building on this first experience, we focussed on identifying the experts and the support necessary to develop the missing pages and soon after, the last domain page and a supplementary tool assembly was released in the RDMkit (Table 3). The work was completed by some use cases with dedicated DSW resources: a new knowledge model dedicated to the management of sensitive human health data and three project templates⁸[1]. This additional work is however not captured in KPI-1.

In parallel, we had a high-level analysis of training gaps in relation with data management planning in the context of all use cases through a survey followed by a series of F2F interviews for all use cases (KPI-4). This work was completed for two of them with the development of a learning path that resulted in a better structuration and detail of these.

⁸ Capella-Gutierrez S, Popleteeva M, Bianchini F, Åberg E, Hooft R, Schuánek M, Slifka J, Hospital A, Willassen NP, Piñero J, Sanz F, Ramirez-Anguila JM, Pastor M, Mayer MA, Picardi E, Alper P, Ded V, Djenaba Barry N, Lieby P, d’Altri T, Faria D, Le Floch E, Rocca-Serra P, Droesbeke B, Bösl K, Vidak M (2023) Deliverable D5.5 Report on the remaining four DMP processes

4.2 Engagement of communities and success stories

4.2.1 - Assessment of dissemination efforts in the context of the use cases

Nine oral communications and one poster were delivered to different public (ELIXIR Communities, data stewards involved in WP1, other projects) mainly in the context of use case 1 and 4 (I-5 = 10).

This indicator does not capture the fact that for instance, members of the ELIXIR Plant Science community as well as of international projects in the domain^{9[1]} were invited to contribute to the development of the RDMkit plant science domain pages and to the identification of training gaps in the context of this use case. As well, it does not capture the fact that the Marine metagenomics RDMkit domain pages were fully co-developed with the ELIXIR Marine metagenomic community.

4.2.2 - Success stories showing interest and adoption by communities of users

Finally, ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP5 started to collect success stories issued from its outputs that are listed below.

Use case 1. Harmonised FAIR plant genotype & phenotype data management toolkit for Europe

- The Plant Science domain pages¹⁰ and its associated Tool Assembly pages^{11,12} have been co-developed and regularly revised with the active contribution of the ELIXIR Plant Science community, which is a good signal for their long term maintenance. This contribution also enriched the RDMkit domain pages with a FAIR Cookbook recipe for the submission of plant sequences to ENA. Indeed, the RDMkit domain pages and the RDMkit portal as a whole constitute a one stop portal that can replace several web sites previously maintained by the members of the community to give guidance on data management.
- The plant science domain pages guidance is currently used in the french node to plan the data management in a large national project aiming at characterising large collections of genetic resources.
- The network of INRAE data stewards has adopted the learning path on Plant phenotyping data management as a frame to improve its training resources and plan to work on it in 2023.

⁹ COST Action 1711 Integrape and H2020 AGENT project

¹⁰ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_sciences

¹¹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_genomics_assembly

¹² https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/plant_phenomics_assembly

Use Case 4 - Federated access to human genomics data: GDPR

- Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) knowledge model (KM) has been developed by Nene Barry (LU), Pinar Alper (LU), Vilem Ded (LU), Paulette Lieby (FR) revised by ELIXIR-LU data stewards during test run and is regularly updated based on user comments. This way of preparing DPIA documents allows granular questions which are easier to understand, detailed guidance and higher independence of researchers.
- DPIA KM in DSW is currently in use at Luxembourg Centre for Systems Biomedicine (LCSB) for preparation of this document on projects involving sensitive human data.
- LCSB data stewards see significant decrease of DPIA workload as involvement of DPIA KM in DSW requires less guidance to researchers.

Use Case 6 - FAIR organisation of biomolecular simulation information

- The creation of the RDMkit domain page on "biomolecular simulation data"¹³ [4] was presented to the ELIXIR structural community (3D-BioInfo) and played a role in convincing them to establish a new domain of work called "Structural bioinformatics."
- Recognition and use of the RDMkit domain page within the structural community indicates its value and impact on the field of biomolecular simulation data:
 - The information presented on the RDMkit page has been incorporated into two European projects, BioExcel and MDDDB, both of which are focused on simulations in biomolecular research.
 - The partners involved in the BioExcel and MDDDB projects have acknowledged the importance of the RDMkit page and have committed to reviewing and updating its content during the execution of these projects.

6. Conclusions

The KPIs developed and collected by WP5 during the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project were useful to follow the partner progresses in the development and test of a sort of starter kit for domain specific data management support that includes:

- RDMkit domain pages and tool assembly

¹³ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/biomolecular_simulation_data

- DSW knowledge model improvements and project templates
- Learning path template

Success stories could be collected in addition, showing adoption by communities and new projects. These success stories are a first assessment of the impact of WP5, as described in the next chapter.

7. Impact

The success stories already collected can be mapped in the different categories of impact that have been developed by WP4 in the framework of ELIXIR-CONVERGE as well as joined activities with other projects^{14,15} as described in table 4. They map on 5/9 of these categories, which is very encouraging in terms of usefulness of the resources developed and of engagement to maintain them beyond the project.

Table 4. Mapping of the success stories collected in the context of the work achieved on use cases in ELIXIR-CONVERGE on ELIXIR's impact categories¹⁵

Impact category - Title	Impact category - Description	ELIXIR-CONVERGE success story
Research efficiency	We make infrastructure, bioinformatics resources and processes faster, easier to use, and more integrated	Adoption of the RDMkit domain pages by new projects in the context of the Plant Science and 3D-Bioinfo communities; adoption of the DPIA-KM by researchers
Scientific legacy	(i.e. research dissemination) We increase awareness of developments related to research infrastructure, bioinformatics resources and related guidelines	Publication of 6 RDMkit domain pages

¹⁴ Martin, CS, Repo, S, Arenas Márquez, J, et al. Demonstrating public value to funders and other stakeholders—the journey of ELIXIR, a virtual and distributed research infrastructure for life science data. *Ann Public Coop Econ.* 2021; 92: 497– 510. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apce.12328>

¹⁵ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/more-examples>

Benefits of working together	(i.e. relationship capital) We facilitate knowledge-sharing and cooperation	Joint activities with projects consortia and ELIXIR communities to maintain and improve DMP guidance in the context of Plant Science and 3D Bioinfo
Public awareness	We raise public awareness of bioinformatics and open science, including their socio-economic and societal benefits	-N/A
Policy influence	We ensure that policy-makers are aware of the benefits of Open (FAIR) Science	-N/A
Equal opportunity	We raise awareness of diversity and inclusiveness	-N/A
Skills development	(i.e. human capital) We foster better skills for users and service providers	Adoption of the learning path by the INRAE network of data steward to improve their training resources
Research infrastructure sustainability	We work to increase ELIXIR's visibility with, and appreciation by, funders.	-N/A
Bioinformatics resource uptake	We work to increase their usage and appreciation by users	Reduction of the workload of ELIXIR-LU's data stewards showing an easy uptake of the DPIA-KM by researchers.

8. Next Steps

Beyond the ELIXIR Project, ELIXIR partners will continue to develop support to DMP by mobilising the domain DPM support starter kit and to improve the resources already developed but the first set of KPIs will not be collected anymore. Communication on these activities will be crucial to continue engaging relevant experts for the improvement of the ecosystem and knowledge hub that is emerging and for its long term sustainability.

We expect new success stories showing adoption and higher efficiency in data management planning and possibly also mapping to new categories of impact such as Research Infrastructure sustainability and policy maker awareness.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

NA

